

Received: 16 October 2022

Revised: 22 November 2022

Accepted: 27 December 2022

DOI: <https://doi.org/>

Research Article

Exploring the Perceptions of SHS Towards the Role of Technology in the New Normal Setting of Education

Irish Mae A. Jalocon¹ | Jade Valerie V. Zonio¹ | Lei Andrei C. Ramos¹ |

¹Malay National High School, Grade II GAS
Philippines

Correspondence
Email:
sherwin.batilantes001@deped.gov.ph

ABSTRACT

The study was conducted to find out the perception of Senior High School Students towards the role of technology in the new normal setting of education. Specifically, it aimed to find out the different problems encountered by students and how did they cope up with the changes brought by the changes in the use of technology. Participants were ten (10) grade II Senior High School students enrolled in Malay National High School and was chosen using the convenience sampling method. Data was gathered using in-depth interview through phone call and face-to-face and was analyzed using the deductive method of thematic analysis. Results suggested that students perceived the role of technology as a communication tool that they used to communicate with their teachers, peers, and relatives. In addition, it also served as a learning aid that helps them in answering and understanding their modules. The results also showed that there are some problems encountered by the students in using technology and those were: technical problems specifically gadgets malfunction and application glitching. They also had difficulty in connectivity, and navigating software applications, developed technology dependence, and they also struggled financially. Students also shared some adjustments that they made to cope with the changes brought by the use of technology during pandemic. Those were: connectivity spot, time adjustments, seeking technical assistance and adjustment in their application manipulative skill.

Copyright: 2023 by the authors. Licensee KMF Publishers (www.kmf-publishers.com). This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has since caused widespread disruptions in schools and universities. Scientists discovered a new infectious disease caused by a novel coronavirus in December 2019. According to Hew et al. (as cited in UNESCO [United Nation Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization], n.d.), 91 percent of the world's student population were affected by school and university closure implemented by more than 188 countries as of April 10, 2020.

Students claim that technology made education in this year of pandemic easier and more accessible. It has evolved and shaped the workplace in many ways, through the adaptation of tools like the internet and email for communications, word of processing, spreadsheets and presentations for office or school productivity, an electronic database for record-keeping, and robots and artificial intelligence for automation.

The effective use of digital learning tools can boost student engagement, assist teachers in improving lesson plans, and enable personalized learning. It also assists students in developing critical 21st-century skills. Virtual classrooms, video, augmented reality (AR), robots, and other technology tools can not only make the class more interesting, but they can also create more inclusive learning environments that foster collaboration and inquisitiveness while also allowing teachers to collect data on student performance. However, it is important to remember that technology is a tool for education, not an end in itself. The promise of educational technology lies in what educators do with it and how they use it to best meet the needs of their students. Teachers want to improve student performance, and technology can assist them in doing so.

Students have discovered that they have difficulties in understanding the words used in the module, difficulty in comprehending instructions, due to lack

of social and physical interaction with teachers and other students, and modules lacking in educational pictures. Two-school years after the implementation, this challenge remains.

The above-mentioned challenges are said to be due to these various reasons: they are suffering from anxiety and depression, poor internet services, difficulties in adjusting to sudden changes in the educational system, absence of gadgets to use, and an unfavorable home learning environment, which were aggravated when students are marginalized and from remote areas. Furthermore, distance learning could also affect their social interaction with other students and decrease their engagement, motivation, and performance in learning (Kapasia et al. 2020 as cited by Barrot et.al., 2021)

Students at Malay National High School also had these challenges facing the New Normal in education. Hence, the researchers conducted this study to determine the perception of students on the role of technology in the new normal setting of education. This research also explores to know what are the common problems that a student is experiencing while using technology in their education and how they overcome the changes that they are encountering regarding the use of technology in studying.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study aimed to find out the students' perception of the role of technology during the pandemic.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

- What are the roles of technology in education during this time of pandemic based on the students' perceptions?
- What are the problems faced by students with regards to the use of technology in education in this time of pandemic?
- How did students cope with the changes brought by the use of technology in this new normal setting of education?

RESEARCH DESIGN

The researcher utilized a qualitative research design and phenomenology research approach in consideration of the nature of the problem under study. This design is grounded in certain traditions of philosophy and the humanities that aim to reflect on the pre-reflective human experience.

This kind of design was selected on account of the usual lived experience shared by all participants [emphasis added] in the span of the study (Lichtman, 2010 as cited in Rehmat & Bailey, 2014, p. 748). Similarly, this design intends to identify and describe how students' perceptions of an online learning environment were influenced by an abrupt extensive transition to online learning (Lemay et al., 2021, p. 2). In addition, it highlights the challenges faced by the students during the global pandemic emergency (Abdur Rehman et al., 2021, p. 259).

Specifically, this study utilized a phone-call and face-to-face interview with the students randomly selected. The researcher primarily asked about students' perceptions of the role of technology in the transition to online learning. Then, the retrieved response(s) were analyzed using the deductive method of thematic analysis.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted at Malay National High School (MNHS), a public secondary school in the Province of Aklan. It is an educational institution geographically situated at Barangay Motag, Malay, Aklan. It is composed of a Junior High School (JHS) and a Senior High School (SHS).

Participants of the Study

The participants of the study were ten (10) Grade 11 SHS students both male and female, who are officially enrolled at Malay National Highschool for S.Y 2021-2022, and willing to participate and give their insights and thoughts about this research study.

Sampling Technique

Convenience sampling was used in choosing the participants of the study. According to Lavrakas (2008) it is a type of nonprobability sampling in which people are sampled simply because they are "convenient" sources of data for researchers.

Moreover, the current situation caused by COVID-19 Pandemic made it difficult for the researchers to retrieve data from the respondents due to some health-related restrictions. Thus, convenience sampling was adopted. They collected data from conveniently available pool of respondents, through phone calls and face to face interview following the minimum health and safety protocols imposed by IATF (Inter-Agency Task Force).

Data Collection

An in-depth interview was used in collecting the data of this study. It is a one-on-one interview conducted by the researcher whose aim is to identify participant's emotions, feelings, and opinions regarding a particular research subject (Langkos, 2014).

The conduct of the research involved the use of questionnaire which was used as an interview guide by the researchers. Questions were prepared by the researchers to guide the interview towards satisfaction of the research objectives then, follow up questions were made during the interview.

Data Analysis

Thematic Analysis is an accessible, flexible, and increasingly popular method of qualitative data analysis. Learning to do it provides the qualitative researcher with a foundation in the basic skills needed to engage with other approaches to qualitative data analysis. In addition, thematic analysis is a method for systematically identifying, organizing, and offering insight into, patterns of meaning (themes) across a dataset (Braun V. & Clarke V., 2012).

The researchers analyzed the data using the deductive method of thematic analysis. They formulated themes and subthemes based on the objectives of the study. Then, they familiarized themselves by transcribing the raw data into readable format and then code the text with the relevant points and keywords. After that the researchers categorized the data into each theme. Lastly, the researchers studied the categorized data and made relevant observations and inferences and crafted the final report of the thematic analysis.

PERCEPTION OF THE ROLE OF TECHNOLOGY DURING THE PANDEMIC

Communication Tools

Communication tools are generally used for external and internal communication. These tools are essential in different areas, especially in the field of education. According to Workvivo (2022), communication tools are a broad label given to apps, software, or online portals that allow dispersed and remote teams to collaborate and talk to each other. Examples of communication tools include mail, e-mail, telephones, cell phones, smartphones, computers, video and web conferencing tools, and social networking. At present, most schools enhance students learning experiences with the help of technology.

In the study conducted by Sedat and Arat (2015), people started to use communication tools for different purposes like using social networking sites where people can communicate with each other, and also they can use these sites for educating their colleagues and giving homework to students.

Student-Teacher Communication

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, face-to-face classes are prohibited, and different learning modalities are adopted. Communication exchange between the student and the teacher is made possible because of the use of technologies through different online platforms. This type of interaction extends learning

beyond the walls of the schools and removes some of the restrictions imposed on learning such as distance and space (Ally & Prieto-Blazquez, 2014; Bansal & Dhananjay, 2014). Some prior research found that social media are tools used by teachers and students to facilitate education (D'Aquila et al., 2019; Holmes & Rasmussen, 2018). The rapid exchange of information and knowledge via social networks has significantly changed student learning (Chugh & Ruhi, 2018; Sharabati, 2018). Social media, which include Facebook, messenger, and other social networks, have profoundly changed the way students and teachers communicate. With the increasing use of social media, the demand for communication and the exchange of information between people is growing (Aydin, 2012).

As quoted by participant A, "Dahil bawal kita maguwa kaya nakabulig imaw sa akon para maka-communicate sa teachers and classmates kung paano namon ubrahon ang activities nga gina pag-aralan namon sa adlaw adlaw nga pagtuon." Participant B also stated, "Ginapadali nana sa amon ang makipag-komunikasyon sa amon teachers at among mga classmates." Moreover, Participant C added, "Para sa akin, ang technology sa edukasyon ngayong pandemic is nakatulong siya ng sobra, lalo na sa aming pakikipagcommunicate sa teachers." These statements are supported by the study conducted by Chugh and Ruhi (2018) in which they had identified multiple benefits of social media usage for teaching and learning such as improved students' performance, attained convenience for learning, and increased engagement between the student and the teacher.

Student-Student Communication

Communication between students is made easy using different communication tools. Online tools such as Facebook, messenger, and other social networks give students more flexible learning experiences. They can collaborate and ask questions to each other even at a distance using different online platforms. Through the use of technology to access online, students can help

each other and work together to better understand the learning material. One of the ways that collaboration through distance learning can be achieved is via synchronous communication (online chat, messaging platforms, virtual classrooms, etc.) where all students can actively engage in communicating from different geographical locations (Duncan et al., 2012).

According to Participant D, “In this time of pandemic, technology is a key para sa amon mga students para maging easy ang amon mga ulubrahon”. Participant E added, “Ang pagamit it online platforms pareho sa messenger hay useful for communication mostly sa amon nga mga estudyante lalo na kaya nga ang school hay nasa modular distance learning ag gaturo sa amon ang mga maestra through online”. These statements are supported by several studies. According to Chan and Chan (2011), using communication tools through online platforms, students can have group discussions and forums where students’ ideas are shared and discussed, which can positively influence collaboration on a project, develop students’ engagement, and improve their academic performance. Moreover, students using Facebook and other social platforms for educational purposes engage more in online communication and collaboration in their studies (Zarzycka, 2021).

Student-Family Members Communication

It is necessary to communicate with parents using different communication tools consistently and systematically. The school should set up clear and consistent communication mechanisms, and a pattern of reaching out to parents, thus, encouraging them to get involved and support their children’s activities at school or home. It is also important for schools to ensure that all parents and students, including the most vulnerable, can access key information by ensuring that communication is developmentally appropriate and accessible for all students.

According to Participant F, “Communication is useful for communicating with teachers and my online friends, relatives that are far away from living in the other country.” It is agreed by Participant G who stated that “Communication tools like Facebook hay importante gid para maka access kita sa aton mga teachers, classmates, family, ag mga siblings.”

These statements are in support of several studies. Whiting and Williams (2013), as well as Papoola (2014), confirm that social media are used to socialize and interact with the family. Moreover, findings revealed that parents reported high satisfaction when the learning materials were delivered by teachers via an online platform as communication tools compared to other methods. (Eickelmann et al., 2019; Ames et al., 2021).

Learning Aids

Learning Aids are tools that can improve education in many ways (Brow, 2019). Teachers, students, as well as parents benefit from free online resources, personalized learning materials, and opportunities for advanced learning. Technology indeed enhances students’ education amidst the pandemic. The use of learning aids such as Google Classroom, Google Meet, Zoom, and other online platforms makes learning more effective. This allows collaboration between the teachers and students in virtual classes as well as communicating in forums and other virtual meetings. Moreover, these learning aids are designed to help students and teachers to communicate, collaborate, organize, and make assignments that are paperless (Bell, 2015). Moreover, the use of these learning aids is expected to improve quality and aid in education, especially in this time of pandemic.

Means for learning

Applications such as Google Classroom, Zoom, and Google Meet are free applications designed to assist students and teachers to connect, work together, organize, and create assignments. It enables learning to be paperless and stores data that students can

access for free. As stated by student participant B “Very helpful kasi diba when it comes sa mga research syempre kailangan naton it internet. Kailangan naton it mga cellphone, mga devices para maka search kung anoa tong kailangan nga sabtan, para makabulig sa aton, when it comes sa mga modules.”

In addition, Google Apps for Education includes web tools like Google Docs, Google Drive, Gmail, etc which all users have easy access to these web tools. Teachers can work together with their students without meeting face to face. Teachers can post materials for their students through this medium, they can also make announcements and create assignments and quizzes for students to complete, submit and save online either in a web the browser or on Google Classroom App which is very helpful in the teaching-learning process in this new normal (Hussaini and Libata, 2020)

PROBLEMS FACED BY STUDENTS WITH REGARDS TO THE USE OF TECHNOLOGY DURING PANDEMIC.

Technical Problems

Technical problems are unexpected issues, such as hardware breakdowns or software defects, that make performing the desired operation difficult or impossible. Consequently, other obstacles faced by students during online learning include the lack of available facilities, and limited internet or network access that interfere with the implementation of online learning (Firmansyah et.al., 2020). Some prior research (Girard, I., 2021) have been reported of students are unable to do their online activities/tasks because of their insufficient or unstable devices.

Gadgets Malfunction

Gadgets malfunction fails to operate the device normally. According to the study by Gierdowski and Brooks (2021), students experienced particular issues with their gadgets that greatly affected their

schoolworks. Thus, they missed classes and deadlines because their gadgets didn't work or weren't equipped for a needed task. Many students are affected by using gadgets or devices that are outdated and/or unable to support the kinds of software and apps required in their class.

Student-participant A quoted, “naga-lag ang cellphone kaya nalisdan ako magsearch”. Student-participants B, agreed, “Low-quality namon nga cellphone hay affected gid lalo na tuwing online class”. Student-participant C said, “Dahil sa pag-over use it amon cellphone, mostly ang effect kato sa gadgets hay ga-lag” Student-participant D also agreed, “Dahil ga-lag imaw, nakakastress dahil di ko magamit ang cellphone pag mag research.” These statements are supported by several studies. According to Plitnichenko (2020), the common problem that students are facing is a gadget malfunction that happens at the most unexpected moment which affected their learning.

Application Glitching

Application Glitches are software errors that cause drastic problems within the code and typically go unnoticed or unsolved during the production of said software. These errors can be game cause or otherwise exploit until a developer/development team repairs them with patches.

Participant E and F experienced this kind of problem. According to participant E, “Since that application that I used has malfunctioned, it is difficult to pass our activity on time”. Participant F agreed that “Once ang amon application hay ga glitch, ga cause imaw it stress sa amon magpasa it mga activities through online”.

These statements were supported by the study from Quello Center Working Paper (2020) that due to poor internet connection, lack of having gadgets, software malfunctions/poor application services, and difficulties in exploring the internet world, greatly

effect's students' performance in performing the task that requires digital skills.

Connectivity Problem

A connectivity problem is an unexpected network failure or poor internet connection that many of the students greatly suffered from kind of problem. In the study conducted by Gierdowski (2021), some students go to great lengths in search of a stable Wi-fi connection, while others don't have the option to go elsewhere and must do without if their service is disrupted.

Student- Participant A quoted, "The problem I experienced is poor internet connection." Student Student-participant B also stated, "Hina ang internet." Student- participant C agreed, "Hirap actually nga hina ang connection tapos napaka unstable it connection." Student participant D, "amat bukon it tuloy tuloy ang internet so medyo struggle imaw mayad, di kaw halos maka sabay sa topic dahil bukon kita it parehas rehas it internet connection... medyo na lelate kaw kung may na sturyahan sanda dahil bukon baskog ang internet nakakatao maw sa akon it problema at amat nadudula maw."

According to Lisa Plitnichenko (2020), millions of people around the world are experiencing technical difficulties because of the high usage rate of online learning systems, video streaming, software, and other digital tools. Some of its reasons are the platforms are overloaded, poor quality video and audio, and internet problems. Thus, students and teachers are indeed trying to manage the bad internet connection during the online lesson.

SOFTWARE APPLICATIONS NAVIGATIONAL DIFFICULTY

Software applications navigational difficulty is the difficulty in using applications. As student participant E quoted that "Amat lang hay...nalisdan mag gamit, may mga ano nga dika kausoy kung pano

gamiton na application." This conforms to the study of Barteby (2021) that this problem creates challenges for students attending online learning because they cannot practice with updated technologies. Therefore, students have some difficulties in doing their learning activities.

Technological Dependence

Students being too dependent on technology has led to students not developing their own thinking and opinions as it is always spoon-feeding them information. Also, online interactions have stripped them of communication skills (Piyush Nawalgaria, 2021). These days students just google to complete their projects and homework. They do not take the trouble of understanding what they are reading, they just copy and paste stuff. It is as if they have sent their brain on a break (Ridhima Mittal, 2021).

One student participant stated this as a major problem during this new normal education. He said that, "The problem that I see in technology is the comfort, what I mean the comfort is that when students use more and more technology on education, it helps them find answers quickly... that they, or we are adopted to kind of fast knowledge, that in just blink on an eye. Because of that, they didn't use their pure potential to learn instead of using their minds to learn something, they use technology to find the answer instead." This statement is supported to the study conducted by Mandi (2021), that over-dependence on technology has led to students losing creativity, and the ability to think and form opinions as a huge source of information is available at the click of a finger. They merely search on Google and other websites to complete their projects and assignments by just clicking the button.

Financial Problems

Students experience financial problems especially in buying gadgets for easy access to online learning. Participants C stated, "Low quality nga cellphone lang amon ginabakal dahil imaw lang kaya it budget

for online class.”. Participants D agreed, “Kawalan ng load hay bahol gid nga balakid para makasulod kami everyday sa amon online class.”

These statements conformed to the study conducted by Lulaj (2022), that research implications suggest that focusing on online learning enhances student performance and that families who have good financial standing have less financial stress to create the conditions for a new learning environment.

ADAPTATIONS MADE BY STUDENTS BROUGHT BY THE USE OF TECHNOLOGY DURING PANDEMIC.

Adjustments

With the new educational setting, students must adapt to the upcoming changes. Students must learn to better manage their time and be more resilient when faced with problems such as a poor internet connection. Khalil et al. (2020) study indicated that students generally perceive synchronous online learning positively, particularly in terms of time management and efficacy. However, they also reported technical (internet connectivity and poor utility of tools), methodological (content delivery), and behavioral (individual personality) challenges. In addition, Gonzales et al. (2020) found that the confinement of students during the pandemic had significant positive effects on their performance. They attributed these results to students' continuous use of learning strategies which, in turn, improved their learning efficiency.

Connectivity spot

Students, generally in rural areas must face the challenge of looking stable internet connection to cope with online learning. According to Kapasia et al. (2020), one of the challenges that students is facing is poor internet service. Thus, differences in-home internet access have direct and indirect effects on

students' achievements. (Quello Center Working Paper, 2020).

As stated by Participant A, “Mausoy it lugar nga may signal it ng cellphone “. Participant B has also the same views. According to her, “Nag usoy gid ako it may signal”. This also agreed by the participant C as she stated that, “Mausoy gid-a it place nga baskog ang signal ag para ma-access nakon ang file”. These statements are supported by the study conducted by Ellen et al. (2020) , which found, that poor internet connectivity was the biggest challenge faced by students. Moreover, this affirms the study of Like and Afif (2020), in which they showed that one of the barriers students experience during online learning is the slow internet connection.

Time adjustments

Due to the current changes in the educational system, the students must learn to manage their time more responsibly or devote more time to certain activities while devoting less time to others.

According to participant D, “Siguro ang adjustments hay, dati bihira lang ako mag adjust it akon time sa pagamit cellphone. Kaya hay mas naka tutok na ako para sa amon online class.” Participant E added, “Siguro nag adjust ako through ano, spending more time sa social media tapos sa kung ano pang platform.” In addition, participant F stated that, “Pagkakaroon ng time management sa paggamit ng gadgets para maiwasan ang pag drain it battery.” These supported by the study of Khalil et al. (2020), which hee indicated that students generally perceive synchronous online learning positively, particularly in terms of time management and efficacy.

Seeking technical assistance

In Fawaz et al.'s (2021) conducted study, he proved that students raised their concerns about learning and evaluation methods, overwhelming task load, technical difficulties, and confinement. To cope with these problems, students actively dealt with these

situations by seeking help from their teachers and relatives. These active-oriented coping mechanisms of students have a positive learning effect (Carter et.al., 2020)

Manipulative skills

To provide education during this pandemic, the students must learn how to use modern technologies like the internet, personal computer, and cellphone (Quello Center Working Paper, 2020).

Participant G stated that, “Nag adjust ako by spending more time sa iba’t ibang platform gaya ng editing. Sa ibis paint, natuto ako mag drawing”. Participant H also stated, “Minaster ko ang applications sa cellphone, yung paggamit ng mahalalagang bagay sa ano files para ma gamit ko ito”. These statements are supported by the study conducted by Murphy (2020). According to her, the knowledge and experience gained may help students with their future abilities and perception of self-efficacy regarding online educational technologies. She also mentioned that the use of emergency e-Learning programs increased the students’ knowledge of technological tools.

IMPLICATIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Students’ perception towards the use of technology in education, can a be a basis in determining the level of acceptance to technology and acquisition of knowledge. The result of this study can contribute to determine the level of technological advancement of the country.

Based on the results of the study, the following recommendations were formulated:

- The parents, teachers and other stakeholders of the school should work together to support their children’s education, and to make sure that children are not left behind the rapidly advancing technology.

- A research study on the factors affecting the perceptions of students towards the role of technology should be conducted.
- The Local Government Unit of Malay will be able to craft and implement projects that would aim to provide technological assistance to learners.

REFERENCES

- FirmansyahR, et.al., (2020). Educational Transformation: An Evaluation of Online Learning Due to COVID-19. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*. www.learntechlib.org/p/220042/
- Gierdowski, D., and Brooks, C. (2021). *EDUCAUSE 2020 Student Technology Report: Supporting the Whole Student*. www.Technology Use and Environmental Preferences | EDUCAUSE
- Girard, I. et.al., (2021). *COVID-19 and Technical Difficulties: The Rise of Inequalities in Higher Education*. [www.Covid-19 and technical difficulties: the rise of inequalities in higher education | Right to Education Initiative \(right-to-education.org\)](http://www.Covid-19 and technical difficulties: the rise of inequalities in higher education | Right to Education Initiative (right-to-education.org))
- Plitnichenko, L. (2020). *EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY*. <https://elearningindustry.com/5-main-roles-artificial-intelligence-in-education>
- Ally, M., & Prieto-Blazquez, J. (2014). What is the future of mobile learning in education? *Revista De Universidad Sociedad Del Conocimiento*, 11(1), 142–151. <https://doi.org/10.7238/rusc.v11i1.2033>
- Aydin, S. (2012). A review of research on Facebook as an educational environment. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 60(6), 1093–1106. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-012-9260-7>
- Chan, C. K. K., & Chan, Y. Y. (2011). Students’ views of collaboration and online participation in Knowledge Forum. *Computers & Education*, 57(1), 1445–1457.

- <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2010.09.003>
- Chugh, R., & Ruhi, U. (2018). Social media in higher education: A literature review of Facebook. *Education and Information Technologies*, 23(2), 605–616. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-017-9621-2>
- D'Aquila, J. M., Wang, D., & Mattia, A. (2019). Are instructor-generated YouTube videos effective in Zarzycka et al., *Cogent Arts & Humanities* (2021), 8: 1953228 <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311983.2021.1953228>
- 8 Page 16 of 20 accounting classes? A study of student performance, engagement, motivation, and perception. *Journal of Accounting Education*, 47, 63–74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaccedu.2019.02.002>
- Duncan, K., Kenworthy, A., & McNamara, R. (2012). The effect of synchronous and asynchronous participation on students' performance in online accounting courses. *Accounting Education*, 21(4), 431–449. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09639284.2012.673387>
- Şimşek, S. & Arat, T. (2015). Communication Tools Used in Teaching and their Effects: An Empirical Study on the T.C. Selçuk University Samples. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*. 174. 2639-2646. [10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.01.946](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.01.946).
- Zarzycka, E. (2021). Distance Learning During The COVID-19 Pandemic: Students' Communication And Collaboration And The Role Of Social Media. *Cogent Arts and Humanities*. Volum 8, 2021. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/23311983.2021.1953228>
- Lavrakas, P. (2008). *Convenience Sampling*. Sage Research Methods. <https://dx.doi.org/10.4135/9781412963947.n105>
- Ackerman, C. (2017). *Coping Mechanisms: Dealing with Life's disappointments in a healthy way*. www. Coping Mechanisms: Dealing with Life's Disappointments in a Healthy Way (positivepsychology.com)
- Barrot, S. et.al. (2021). Students' online learning challenges during the pandemic and how they cope with them: The case of the Philippines. *National Library of Medicine*. [10.1007/s10639-021-10589-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-021-10589-x)
- Ally, M., & Prieto-Blazquez, J. (2014). What is the future of mobile learning in education? *Revista De Universidad Sociedad Del Conocimiento*, 11(1), 142–151. <https://doi.org/10.7238/rusc.v11i1.2033>
- Aydin, S. (2012). A review of research on Facebook as an educational environment. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 60(6), 1093–1106. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-012-9260-7>
- Chan, C. K. K., & Chan, Y. Y. (2011). Students' views of collaboration and online participation in Knowledge Forum. *Computers & Education*, 57(1), 1445–1457. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2010.09.003>
- Chugh, R., & Ruhi, U. (2018). Social media in higher education: A literature review of Facebook. *Education and Information Technologies*, 23(2), 605–616. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-017-9621-2>
- D'Aquila, J. M., Wang, D., & Mattia, A. (2019). Are instructor-generated YouTube videos effective in Zarzycka et al., *Cogent Arts & Humanities* (2021), 8: 1953228 <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311983.2021.1953228>
- 8 Page 16 of 20 accounting classes? A study of student performance, engagement, motivation, and perception. *Journal of Accounting Education*, 47, 63–74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaccedu.2019.02.002>
- Duncan, K., Kenworthy, A., & McNamara, R. (2012). The effect of synchronous and asynchronous participation on students' performance in online accounting courses. *Accounting*

- Education, 21(4), 431-449.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09639284.2012.673387>
- Şimşek, S. & Arat, T. (2015). Communication Tools Used in Teaching and their Effects: An Empirical Study on the T.C. Selcuk University Samples. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*. 174. 2639-2646. [10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.01.946](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.01.946).
- Zarzycka, E. (2021). Distance Learning During The COVID-19 Pandemic: Students' Communication And Collaboration And The Role Of Social Media. *Congent Arts and Humanities*. Volum 8, 2021. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/23311983.2021.1953228>
- Dennis H. Meier. & Stephan L. Thomsen & Johannes Trunzer (2022). The Financial Situation of students during the COVID-19 Pandemic IZA DP no. 15110 <https://docsiza.org/dp15110.pdf>
- Lisa Plitnichenko 2020. 10 Challenges of E-learning during COVID 19 <https://jellyfish.tech/10-challenges-of-e-learning-during-covid-19/>
- D.Christopher Brooks & Dana C. Gierdowski 2021. Student Experiences with Technology in the Pandemic <https://library.educause.edu/resources/2021/4/student-experiences-with-technology-in-the-pandemic>
- Bartleby.com 2021. Challenges for Students with Software Development <https://www.bartleby.com/essay/Challenges-For-Students-iWith-Software-Development-FKAXZTWKPVDX>
- Debarpita Mandi 2021. Students are becoming more too dependent on technology <https://www.telegripindia.com/education/s-tudents-are-becoming-too-dependent-on-technology-cid/1826841>